

BENZYLTHIOUREAS. PART II

BY J. P. TRIVEDI AND J. J. TRIVEDI

Several monosubstituted benzylthioureas and 1-(*p*-substituted benzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)- and 3-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-thioureas have been synthesised.

In continuation of our previous work (Shah, Trivedi and Trivedi, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 423), several substituted thioureas have been described in the present communication. Huebner *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2274) reported the high antitubercle activity of 4:4'-disubstituted thiocarbanilides. 4-Ethoxy-4'-dimethylaminothiocarbanilide exceeded the activity of PAS and streptomycin and approached that of isoniazide (Lisman *et al.*, *Am. Rev. Tubercle*, 1954, 70, 121, 130).

p-Chlorobenzyl- and *p*-bromobenzyl-thioureas were found to show higher antibacterial and antifungal activity as compared to benzylthiourea (Miss Shah, Ph.D. thesis, Bombay Univ., 1957). This prompted us to prepare thioureas containing halogen- and alkoxy-substituted benzyl group as well as alkoxy and dimethylaminophenyl groups in the same molecule. With this end in view, 1-(*p*-chlorobenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)-, 1-(*p*-bromobenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)-, 1-(*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)- and 1-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-3-(*p*-halogen- or alkoxy-substituted benzyl)-thioureas have been prepared and described in the present communication. A few methyl-, dimethyl- or methoxy-substituted benzylthioureas as well as α -phenylalkyl-thioureas have also been synthesised.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mono- and dimethyl substituted benzylamines were prepared from the corresponding substituted benzyl halides by the method of Graymore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1116).

Methoxybenzylamines were prepared from the corresponding aldehydes by the Leuckart reaction (Ettlinger and Lunden, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1953). α -Phenylethyl-, α -phenylpropyl- and α -phenyl-*n*-butylamines were prepared by the Leuckart reaction of acetophenone, propiophenone and butyrophenone (Ingersoll, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 1808).

p-Ethoxy- and *p*-*n*-butoxybenzylamines were prepared by reduction of oximes of the corresponding aldehydes ("Org. synthesis", Coll. Vol. 11, 1943, p. 318).

p-Aminophenyl alkyl ethers were prepared by reduction of *p*-nitrophenyl alkyl ethers, prepared according to Weygand and Gabler (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1940, 155, 132) and Gray and Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1469).

Amines were converted into isothiocyanates in 60% yield according to the procedure described previously (*loc. cit.*). The isothiocyanates prepared are described in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Benzyl isothiocyanates.

Compound. X =	R =	B.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	H	98°/5 mm	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ONS	16.5	16.6
<i>p</i> -n-OC ₄ H ₉	H	142-45°/10	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ ONS	14.2	14.5
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	H	120°/7	C ₉ H ₉ NS	19.5	19.6
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	H	148°/15	"	19.5	"
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	155°/17	"	19.5	"
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ *	H	132°/5-7	C ₉ H ₉ ONS	17.8	17.9
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	H	128°/3	"	17.8	"
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ †	H	125°/7	...	...	...
2 CH ₃ (3 : 4)	H	170°/12	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NS	18.0	18.1
2 CH ₃ (2 : 4)	H	120°/50	"	18.0	"
2 CH ₃ (2 : 5)	H	160°/9	"	18.0	"
H	CH ₃	140°/5	C ₉ H ₉ NS	19.6	19.6
H	C ₂ H ₅	160°/3	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NS	18.0	18.1
H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	130°/10	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NS	16.7	16.7

* Kjaer *et al.*, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 26.† V. Braun *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1912, 43, 2191.

TABLE II

p-n-Alkoxyphenyl isothiocyanates.

Compound X =	B.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
-OCH ₃ *	280°	...	...	...
-OC ₂ H ₅ *	(M.P.) 76°	...	...	...
<i>n</i> -OC ₃ H ₇	160°/12 mm,	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ONS	16.5	16.6
<i>n</i> -OC ₄ H ₉	170°/15	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ONS	15.1	15.4
<i>n</i> -OC ₆ H ₁₁	170°/15	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ ONS	14.1	14.4
<i>n</i> -OC ₈ H ₁₇	180°/7	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ ONS	13.1	13.6

* Dyson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 443.† Dyson, *ibid.*, 1927, 1705.

Substituted benzylthioureas, shown in Table III, were prepared as described previously (*loc. cit.*); yield 40 to 50%.

1-(*p*-Chlorobenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)-thioureas were prepared by condensation of *p*-chlorobenzyl isothiocyanate with the corresponding *p*-*n*-alkoxy-anilines according to Buu-Hoï *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1573) in 60% yield

1-(*p*-Bromobenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)-thioureas were prepared by condensation of *p*-bromobenzyl isothiocyanate with the corresponding *p*-*n*-alkoxy-anilines according to Buu-Hoï *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) in 60% yield.

1-(*p*-Ethoxybenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)-thioureas and 1-(*p*-*n*-butoxybenzyl)-3-(*p*-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)-thioureas were prepared by condensation of *p*-ethoxybenzyl isothiocyanate and *p*-*n*-butoxybenzyl isothiocyanate respectively with the corresponding *p*-*n*-alkoxy-anilines according to Buu-Hoï (*loc. cit.*) in 60% yield.

1-(*p*-Substituted benzyl)-3-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-thioureas were prepared by condensation of *p*-substituted benzyl isothiocyanates with *p*-dimethylaminoaniline according to Buu-Hoï *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) in 60% yield. These compounds are described in Table IV.

TABLE III

Substituted benzylthioureas.

Compound.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
X=	R=			Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	106°	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	17.4	17.8
2 CH ₃ (3 : 4)	H	120°	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	16.3	16.5
2 CH ₃ (2 : 5)	H	110°	"	16.4	"
<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	H	145°	C ₉ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	16.1	16.3
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	H	102°	"	16.3	"
H	CH ₃	147°	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	17.7	17.8
H	C ₂ H ₅	133°	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	16.3	16.5
H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	98°	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	15.2	15.4

TABLE IV
 1-(p-Substituted benzyl)-3-(p-substituted phenyl)-thioureas
 $X - C_6H_4CH_2 - NHCSNH - C_6H_4R$.

R =	Compound. X =	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
-OCH ₃	Cl	132°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	Cl : 11.4%	11.6%
-OC ₂ H ₅	Cl	148°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₂ ClS	Cl : 11.0	11.1
n-OC ₃ H ₇	Cl	120°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ ON ₂ ClS	Cl : 10.5	10.6
n-OC ₄ H ₉	Cl	110°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ON ₂ ClS	Cl : 9.9	10.2
n-OC ₅ H ₁₁	Cl	86°	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON ₂ ClS	Cl : 9.7	9.8
n-OC ₆ H ₁₃	Cl	92°	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ON ₂ ClS	Cl : 9.2	9.4
-OCH ₃	Br	147°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₂ BrS	Br : 22.7	22.8
-OC ₂ H ₅	Br	135°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₂ BrS	Br : 21.9	21.9
n-OC ₃ H ₇	Br	120°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ ON ₂ BrS	Br : 20.9	21.1
n-OC ₄ H ₉	Br	154°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ON ₂ BrS	Br : 20.1	20.3
n-OC ₅ H ₁₁	Br	93°	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON ₂ BrS	Br : 19.6	19.6
n-OC ₆ H ₁₃	Br	96°	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ON ₂ BrS	Br : 18.7	19.0
-OCH ₃	-OC ₂ H ₅	113°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 10.0	10.1
-OC ₂ H ₅	-OC ₃ H ₇	98°	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 9.6	9.7
n-OC ₃ H ₇	-OC ₄ H ₉	78°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 9.2	9.3
n-OC ₄ H ₉	-OC ₅ H ₁₁	83°	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 8.9	8.9
n-OC ₅ H ₁₁	-OC ₆ H ₁₃	61°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 8.5	8.6
n-OC ₆ H ₁₃	-OC ₂ H ₅	56°	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 8.2	8.3
-OCH ₃	n-OC ₄ H ₉	175°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 9.2	9.3
-OC ₂ H ₅	n-OC ₄ H ₉	96°	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 8.9	8.9
n-OC ₃ H ₇	n-OC ₄ H ₉	85°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 8.6	8.6
n-OC ₄ H ₉	n-OC ₄ H ₉	71°	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 8.1	8.3
n-OC ₅ H ₁₁	n-OC ₄ H ₉	135°	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 7.9	8.0
n-OC ₆ H ₁₃	n-OC ₄ H ₉	73°	C ₂₄ H ₃₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	S : 7.6	7.7
-N(CH ₃) ₂	Cl	139°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ ClS	S : 10.0	10.0
-N(CH ₃) ₂	Br	148°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ BrS	S : 8.7	8.8
-N(CH ₃) ₂	-OCH ₃	108°	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON ₂ S	S : 10.0	10.1
-N(CH ₃) ₂	-OC ₂ H ₅	69°	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ ON ₂ S	S : 9.7	9.7
-N(CH ₃) ₂	n-OC ₄ H ₉	120°	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ ON ₂ S	S : 8.9	8.9

The authors thank Dr. R. D. Desai for interest in the work and the Ahmedabad Education Society for defraying the expenses incurred during the course of this work.